

D3.3.

Playbook

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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List of Abbreviations

CS: Case Study

WSIS: Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis

Executive Summary

This deliverable 3.3, playbook comes from Task 3.1 (Immersive experiences in multi use play spaces) and provides a citizen participation playbook with instructions, protocols and guidelines for designing and implementing the immersive experience¹.

The outcome will be a playbook for stakeholder engagement to be implemented in Task 3.2 (Business-to-business engagement) and 3.3 (Citizen engagement). ULTIMATE`s playbook bring together designers, strategist, developers and the citizens from various backgrounds as a team who can use the ULTIMATE playbook as an engagement tool. The playbook is useful in a team setting and aims to integrate knowledge dissemination in ULTIMATE`s case studies and lead them on how to start the stakeholder engagement process. The playbook will help the case studies and partners start conversations around complex topics that are hard to grasp at first thereby closing the differences and gaps that exist in a multi-stakeholder collaboration practice.

This will make it possible to design and implement the stakeholder engagement for the use case studies CS2 (NL), CS3 (IT), and CS9 (DK). The playbook will be used in D3.6 for validating developed immersive narratives for citizens. Validation will measure the success of the approaches we co-created and implemented and will come in the form of perceived quality of experience which is a subjective measure.

The developed playbook support stakeholders and citizens co-creation process in the ULTIMATE project. This is implemented through scoping their questions, identifying relevant community concerns, planning an effective action and prototyping it to test its impact with the users before development. The playbook will guide them to gather data and evidence, interpret their findings, and develop better understanding of the community and their needs. This will allow them to formulate a design that will lead to a tangible outcome – an immersive experience.

Method

We have formulated a citizen participation playbook with instructions, protocols and guidelines for designing and implementing the immersive experience drawn from our years of experience in co-creation with communities and development of an immersive narrative experience in public spaces.

Since 2016, NTNU have been collaborating with diverse team of artists, scientists, researchers, designers and architects working on tools related to the concepts of multi-use playspaces², place by design and immersive narrative experiences. We have implemented all these concepts in public spaces in Trondheim and on a EU project called +CityxChange³. We have also examined several local intervention sites

¹ An immersive experience is a perception of being present in an environment when you are actually in another reality, creating a feeling of immersion or suspension of disbelief using a number of different technologies.

² https://folk.ntnu.no/wendyann/Adressaparken_toolkit/

³ +CityxChange, under grant agreement no. 824260. <https://cityxchange.eu/>

in connection to the use of tools for engaging communities and have successfully co-created installations and interventions using art, science, and technology.

As a Work Package 3 (WP3) team lead, we selected three use case studies (CS2, CS3 and CS9) that will validate the playbook. We also examined the transactions, activities, potential players and of the case studies so we can decide on the appropriate tools to adopt or use. We revisited the lessons we learned from our previous experiences in the co-creation process and in our implementations of multi-use playspaces, place by design and immersive narrative experiences to provide a new dimension in solving challenges in stakeholder engagements applied in a water-oriented world. Selected tools from our best practices were adopted and tested through internal workshops with our diverse team of artists, scientists, researchers, designers and architects at our Sense-IT⁴ Lab at NTNU. We use a Human-centred design thinking in our formulation of tools and methodologies in the current Playbook. The result of our case study co-creation process will impact the final outcome and legacy of the D3.3 ULTIMATE Playbook.

Conclusion

This report presents a citizen participation playbook with instructions, protocols and guidelines for co-creating the design and initial prototype in the development an immersive narrative intervention.

This deliverable covers the first version of the two playbooks that we are distributing within the ULTIMATE project. It covers 7 stages of co-creation framework: 1. Plan; 2. Understand; 3. Imagine, 4. Reflect, 5. Build, 6. Analyse, 7. Legacy. The first 4 stages: Plan, Understand, Imagine and the first part of Reflect will be validated in the first quarter of 2022. The remaining stages will be validated during the second and third quarter of 2022. To fully realise and validate the playbook as a viable tool, it must be put into practice. D3.3 is highly interlinked with the results of D3.4, which validates the current playbook during the use case study co-creation practice. The formulation of the final version of the playbook will require adaptation based on the outcome of the co-creation process in our case studies.

To fully realise and validate the playbook as a viable tool, it must be put into practice. The playbook as a tool can relatively save time, cost and resources of the public in terms of implementation. Ensuring transparent and creative co-creation with citizens and stakeholders may require a bit more time investments and this playbook ensures flexible, time effective, and impactful implementation. It also enhances the goodwill, trust and influence that the community earn or build up with the public through the pursuit of solutions to concerns that people need.

⁴ <http://www.iet-multimedialabs.org/>

1. Introduction

1.1. What is the purpose of the playbook?

ULTIMATE`s playbook bring together designers, strategist, developers and the citizens from various backgrounds as a team who can use the ULTIMATE playbook as an engagement tool. The playbook is useful in a team setting and aims to integrate knowledge dissemination in ULTIMATE`s case studies and lead them on how to start the Stakeholder engagement process.

Our ULTIMATE playbook`s goal is to enable collaboration and close the differences and gaps that exist in a multi-stakeholder ecosystem. A playbook will help the case studies and partners start conversations around complex topics that are hard to grasp at first. For example, by asking questions such as: How might we solve community issues related to our practice? The playbook acts as a tool to help them break down these obstacles and start working with their relevant challenges

1.2. How the stakeholders can use the playbook?

The playbook includes canvases or plays composed of instructions and templates that are designed for co-creation in teams. Plays are ways of answering questions and developing new ideas through activities. Stakeholders can use them by sketching the templates on a big wall or whiteboard, so participants can gather around it and contribute actively. It is recommended that a facilitator prepares, keeps track of time, and navigates through the activities.

Plays are organised in a suggested order but can be reorganised according to the needs of the case studies. Each play requires a rough time estimate. However, this varies depending on the case study`s challenge, so the facilitator should decide how long they are going to spend for each exercise.

In the second version of the playbook deliverable (Due date: M27), we will provide “case studies in action” section that will show the outcomes of the co-creation alongside the commitment and effort that our case studies have put into creating impactful results.

The playbook will teach ULTIMATE stakeholders and citizens on how to scope their questions, identify relevant community concerns, and plan an effective action. It will then help them gather data and evidence, interpret their findings, build social awareness, which is designed to lead to tangible outcomes. Finally, the playbook will show stakeholders and citizens on how to reflect on these outcomes and offers recommendation on how to leave a lasting and far-reaching impact.

2. The Playbook strategy

2.1. Stakeholder Engagement

As part of our stakeholder engagement model (see Figure1), we started out by exploring what our aspiring Living Labs need to upscale innovation. As part of the co-innovation process, engagement of stakeholder plays a key role. We present a

stakeholder engagement model that includes communities of practice and Co-creation. The co-creation process involves local communities, general public and the industry in creating changes and action by providing them a safe space to gather, reflect, and find new solutions to common challenges. All the methodologies and tools used in our co-creation practice will reflect in the current ULTIMATE Playbook where we will formulate human-centred best practices and approaches used in our co-creation practice and disseminate them as a toolkits and methodologies. The result of our co-creation as a best practice will lead to the development of an immersive narrative experience. This multi-stage approach in our stakeholder engagement aims to ensure long-term and far-reaching impact of change where there may be continued progress in the communities we have formed through the ULTIMATE co-creation, in the knowledge that we have explored and learned; and in the tools and methodologies that we have used and formulated together as a team and as a partner.

Figure 1 ULTIMATE's Stakeholder Engagement

2.2. Immersive digital narratives to transform consumer and public habits and perception

Many industries and organisations have realised the need to re-align themselves to a more sustainable public perception of their company's societal impact or narrative. Transitioning to a more sustainable and community centric approach, however, is more than just an awareness campaign, it requires a value-added service and support system that changes the perception of people. Google Research in their report entitled "Cities in the Circular Economy" for instance is promoting digital technology's big role in transitioning to circular or more sustainable economy.

Changing habits and perceptions requires capacity development and changing the infrastructure and services in place, which can be addressed by providing tools and a safe space that are designed in a modular and flexible manner; allowing creativity, public discourses, place interventions and innovation to thrive, thus activating the concept of "place by design" and adding enablers to facilitate art and digital narratives such as interactive art interventions using immersive tools (using virtual reality, augmented reality and sensing tools), digital asset management tools (tagging and tracking the availability of assets, tools, and materials that can be used or re-used; promoting a multi-use playspace" model), real-time or geo-spatial data (visualisation platform using immersive system to address and predict data in the implementation of place specific interventions), and lastly, connectivity and mobility systems (to sustainably connect assets to those who would like to use them on demand).

To shape our streets, cities, neighbourhood and our future, we need to collaborate using arts and technology in order to create new and powerful forms of community action and learning. We need a playbook to address challenges in working together, developing collective understanding of complex issues and inspiring others to take action. Collaboration and participation is complex, and playbooks can shed light on a number of techniques and tools that can help community organisations to deliver impactful campaigns, interventions, awareness and community actions in a new way.

3. Conclusion

This report presents a citizen participation playbook with instructions, protocols and guidelines for co-creating the design and initial prototype in the development an immersive intervention.

The developed playbook is designed in such a way to optimally support stakeholders and citizens co-creation process in the ULTIMATE project. This is done through scoping their questions, identifying relevant community concerns, planning an effective action and prototyping it to test its impact with the users before development. The playbook will guide them to gather data and evidence, interpret their findings, and develop better understanding of the community and their needs. This will allow them to formulate a design that will lead to an immersive intervention or community action.

4. Annex

Annexed in this deliverable is attached file in PDF form entitled, The ULTIMATE Playbook V1.

Annex 1: ULTIMATE Playbook Version 1

ULTIMATE Playbook

Guide for ULTIMATE Co-Creation

Version 1

Formulating human-centered approaches, methodologies, tools, and protocols to guide and motivate people to do things together, disseminate, use and re-use information in a new way.

Who we are

ULTIMATE is a 4 year Horizon2020 project under the EU Water in the Context of the Circular Economy programme. The aim is to create economic value and increase sustainability by valorising resources within the water cycle.

We developed a collaborative approach as a way of working within our unique ecosystem and we wanted to share it through this playbook to make sure that you as our audience will benefit from it too. We believe that you will find it a useful model to explore.

Within the ULTIMATE project we believe that co-creation process has an ability to positively transform and innovate a place. It is clear, simple, agile and reusable, which helps us to easily realise and co-design solutions together in a physical or an online space.

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How to use this Playbook?

This is our co-creation playbook, describing a number of ‘plays’ that we have used and found helpful in guiding co-creation activities. Plays are ways of answering questions and developing new ideas through activities and they help us to understand challenges, people, practices, and industry more deeply.

Our co-creation results are guided by the concept of a “Place by Design”. The result of our co-creation will lead to co-designed interventions in our selected case study locations.

Get familiar with the content and templates provided to best engage your teams in all these sessions.

After each plays, remember to share your experiences with your team. Refer to the Reflect module to guide you on this process further.

As co-creation is a collaborative endeavour, we welcome input and feedback. We are keen to hear how you use this playbook in your own organisations.

Icons in this Playbook

Here's
your
tip

Guidelines

Exemplar

Questions

What's your role?

As a participant engaging in a play, you must have an open-mind and an agile mindset. It's all about thinking through together how you can understand what's going on in the environment, identify what uncertainty you're facing and will be facing in the future and figure out how to adapt as you go along leading at the team's ability to become more adept at addressing issues at hand.

This playbook is intended to help your blend-in to your new team. If you are an activist or are motivated to take action for the benefit of your community, you will find that this resource is valuable for you to connect yourself to organizations which support community actions. If you are a researcher, an artist, or a designer, this playbook will guide you on how to empower citizens on your research and incorporate art and technologies in your co-creation projects.

Each of you can take turns in leading your team. You can assign a different leader for every plays. As a leader, you will be responsible for creating a great social experience for your team, encourage creativity and learn by doing. Some familiarity with guiding teams and a little preparation will help in facilitating the plays in this playbook.

You can be in charge of simple things - timing each plays, taking notes, documenting your process, capturing photos, or collecting materials. To play your role well, we invite you to set the tone that leads to creativity. Just be open, kind and flexible to others - all the plays in this playbook are meant for you to enjoy doing things with others. Have fun with the plays!

Strategy

General Tips to Run the Co-creation Plays

Questions about content: You might be asked or might have a similar question in your mind: “How are we supposed to answer this question? What is that you expect us to say here?”, etc. It is important to understand that most plays creates context for the team, and therefore all answers are valid. You can think of it this way: ‘What do you think the answer should be?’

Conversations taking time: If some conversations take rather long or touching upon bigger issues, consider parking those questions during the plays. Best to plan a separate meeting to address them in detail.

Tips to Document the Co-creation Plays

Take notes. The act of taking notes is crucial in uncovering tacit knowledge. You will only discover much of what you have learned once you start to write about it. By taking notes you solidify your tacit knowledge, enabling you to reflect and build on it.

Collect materials. Don't document only the things you think is worthy of documenting. Collect materials when you are observing people and places. Collect those leaflets in the train stations. Figure out where all the crowds are gathering together in a relevant place for instance. You will discover value on things or scenarios that you will never expect.

Take photos. Taking photos is an effective way to capture your process without disrupting your workflow. These photos will enable you to reflect on what you have learned after the actual plays. We do not need to think about the quality of your photos, any camera will do the job.

Co-creation

In a world where the pace of change is increasing, the traditional approach of leaving a problem in the hands of the experts is no longer sufficient to deal with the complexity of the many issues we are now facing. Instead, experts and users have to co-create and join others in learning how to address challenges and come up with solutions together.

Co-creation is a collaborative process where experts' work closely with local people, end-users and stakeholders using various resources and ideas to propose, discuss and prototype new actions and solutions to relevant issues. It involves joint creation of value by various participants, allowing them to co-construct the service experience to suit their needs, context and preference. It is a collaboration or partnership – a creative thinking approach.

Co-creation is practiced using methods and tools for people to work together in a playing field, a playground. Through co-creation, all participants can come together with others to find common ground and potential solutions on issues that they identified and defined together through an open dialogue, and reflection of each other's unique perspective.

In our co-creation process, we will employ plays and problem-solving activities to get to know how our participants work not just as an individual but also as a team. It's important for a team to learn to develop strategies, which will help them quickly overcome obstacles in the way of achieving project goals.

Following a co-creation process, a report with suggestions for future actions can be drafted to provide an early prototype needed for future development of a service, action, or an intervention and to begin conversations with decision-makers.

Why Co-create?

We believe that as a participant, you will benefit from the co-creation process because it has the ability to positively transform and create new forms of community action, social engagement and citizen involvement. Locally relevant stakeholders including citizens are invited to contribute, to share their stories, their ideas and to refine, as well as prioritise ideas shared by others in a systematic multi-stage process. Co-creation is utilised throughout the project development process to ensure that new ideas or solutions serve their intended purpose.

By investing in this approach, we envision that our partners increase in idea capacity and velocity: ensuring innovation, reducing risk, building a sense of community, project ownership and engagement.

By co-creating the future we want to envision, and doing so in synchrony with those who experienced the issue to begin with, we can generate and accommodate various ideas, we can predict risks before they happen, and optimally create a solution that works for everyone.

SPREAD AWARENESS

Demonstrate and integrate creative methods, tools and protocols into real practice to scale up innovation and engagement

RAISE AWARENESS

Comprehend and clearly express the benefits of innovation and the need for a safe space where change is possible

BRING INTO PLAY

Develop creative ideas into action and tangible solution (through co-creation, prototyping, and setting-up pilots

Scope

At this first stage, the important challenges are mapped, identified and discussed by the key participants. Potential contributions needed to kick start this co-creation practice are also discovered. Relevant information is collected by Internet searches; documenting reports, articles, and literature; or by conducting interviews and surveys.

Play:

1

Community Concern Map

Identify concerns of the community in relation to the challenges you are facing.

2

Team Map

Map out relevant stakeholders and communities you need to recruit into the project.

Play 1:

Community Concern Map

Identify concerns of the community in relation to the challenges you are facing.

Duration: 60 minutes

Participants: Project team, coordinators, community

Location: Physical meeting room or online.

What is it?

In the early stages, it might be a daunting task to decide how to identify the concerns of those in the community in relation to the challenges you are facing as an organisation, we recommend you to explore the Community Concern Map before proceeding to the next stage. We will use geographical mapping to help you map out realistically both the nature and location of concern hotspots. You can easily use this method to cross reference these hotspots with factual data, connections and associations related to that area.

Where is the issue?

How did you discover it?

Why is the issue there?

Instructions

Step 1. Discuss and locate the concern spots as a team.

1. Locate the spot where the issues in your organization are forming. Mark them in red
2. Locate the spot where the issues in your community are forming. Mark them in blue.
3. Locate the areas where issues intersect most. Mark them in yellow.

Step 2. Discuss the aspects of this issue.

It is important to discuss its seriousness and as well its importance to the community.

Step 3. Record key insights

Write down all the concerns of the community that intersects with your identified challenges.

To give your team time to reflect, you can also first do this task individually and then discuss the results and agree on a common map.

Location: Kalundborg

Legend

Possible concerns:

Community concerns

Intersecting concerns

Play 2:

Team Map

Map out relevant stakeholders and communities you need to recruit into the project.

Duration: 60 minutes to a day

Participants: Project team, coordinators

Location: Physical meeting room or online.

What is it?

Building your community and team is one of most important element for your project. Each community is unique, however, you need to find a balance among constituencies to maintain the right level of participation. Aside from a small core group that engages and nurture the team and the community, you would need active participants who are recognized practitioners and define the community. You can also discuss amongst your team the type of occasional participants (or those who participates only on special topics or interests) you can bring onto your team. You might also consider bringing on board those who with less engagement but has sustained connection to the community. It is also important to consider outsiders who can gain access to artifacts from the community and provide technical and social expertise, or tools that your project requires.

What are the backgrounds, skillsets, and level of participation your team needs ?

In which communities can you locate them?

Instructions

Step 1. Map out the background experiences and skillsets your team needs. We suggest to keep the scope broad and consider the skillsets and experiences that will bring value to the project.

Step 2. Map out the type and level of participation your team needs. Consider the balance of constituencies between various levels of participation your project requires.

Step 3. Consider where you can reach these people. What social environment are they likely to be found?

Step 4. Go ahead and use your recruitment tools and strategies to bring these people on board.

Here is an example of how we mapped our team and potential resource persons in practice. We use stickies on the wall, map the names of people we need and are available within our reach, their skillset and potential level of participation and contribution.

Understand

This is the second stage of the ULTIMATE Co-creation session where we will learn about ourselves as a team and the audience of the immersive experience narrative intervention we later want to develop. We will also understand the challenges and opportunities developing around an action or intervention idea.

Plays:

1

Team Building and Alignment

Engage and know your co-creation team.

2

Audience Empathy Mapping

Find out who the audience are and what they do, feel, and think.

3

On-site Experience Safari and Shadowing

Immerse the team in the environment where the intervention will live.

Play 1:

Team Building and Alignment

Engage and know your co-creation team

Duration: 90 minutes

Participants: Project team, community

Location: Preferably in a physical meeting room

What is it?

This is the time to start engaging people and bringing different types of community stakeholders onboard who have different skills and motivations. With ULTIMATE's co-creation focusing on citizen participation which all is about people coming together to address a challenge or concern, team and community building is the key to this concept. Team and Community building is also about developing relationships between different people from various skills and background - such as people with experience and knowledge of the concerns or issue we are trying to solve. This is an important step since people with various backgrounds ranging from government members to community representatives need to understand one another.

What needs to be done?

It is important to plan the management and governance of the project teams, and determine how the citizen participants and the community in general will align with the project goals. It can be useful at this stage to identify potential contributions the project need in the community and to plan how you might bring onboard these needed skills and contributions to tackle any gaps.

For the project team, it is important to plan how the team is going to document your progress, as well as considering any surveys which might show evidence of changes in behaviours in your community as a result of the current co-creation practice and the future immersive narrative implementation.

How are we doing it ?

We will use the Team Building and Alignment play called Team Canvas to get to know each member of the team in this co-creation practice. We are hoping this activity will also gather enough momentum to get started with the project.

Team canvas is a tool that can help align new teams or re-align existing teams and be good at understanding common goals, roles and values of your team in working on a project. It is composed of several sections with guiding questions that are requested to go through as a team.

When using a Team Canvas, it is good to keep in mind that it consists of 4 parts.

- 1. What the team is:** roles and goals (both common and personal)
- 2. Why the team is doing what it's doing:** purpose and values
- 3. Who are the team members:** their strengths, weaknesses and needs
- 4. How the team is going to achieve what it needs to achieve:** rules and activities

Instructions

Step 1. People & Roles

Put your names on stickies, as well as your roles. If you have multiple roles, use separate post-its.

Questions:

- What are our names?
- What are the roles we have?
- How are we called as a team?

Examples:

- Andrew: Management
- Annika: Administration
- Merkel: CEO
- Team Name: Agile Team

Step 2. Common goals

Discuss as a team and agree on common goals.

Questions:

What you as a group really want to achieve? What is our feasible, measurable and time-bounded key goal within this project?

Example:

- Engage people through sports and involve both young and old people.

Step 3. Personal Goals

Ask yourselves what your individual goals are for the project.

Questions:

What are our personal goals or agendas for this project that we want to share or open up?

Example:

- Marie: Learn about digital technologies.

Step 4. Purpose

Take a step beyond your common goal as a team, and think together why you do what you do.

Questions:

Why are we doing what we are doing?
What purpose make us pursue our common goal?

Examples:

- Create positive impact on people's lives through social innovation
- Make people's life easier and comfortable through Internet of Things.

Step 5. Values

What are the core values of your team? Pick the most important principles that everyone agrees on.

Questions:

- What do we stand for?
- What are our guiding principles?
- What are our common values as a team?

Examples:

- Transparency
- Creativity
- Respect
- Mutual Understanding
- Flexibility

Step 6. Strengths and Assets

Share key pieces of skills (both hard and soft skills) and assets available within the team. Don't dismiss 'insignificant stuff'. You might find that the team has capacity for knitting, running on marathons or social skills. Share something about yourselves, as well as note important qualities you see in your teammates.

Questions:

- Do we have any skills that will help us to achieve our goals?
- What is our interpersonal/soft skills?
- What are we good at, individually and as a team?

Examples:

- Design
- Sales and pitching
- Humour
- Painting
- Leadership

Step 7. Weaknesses and Development Areas

Share your key weaknesses and areas for improvement as well as obstacles you face as a team member. Report on what you can find in yourself rather than discussing other's weaknesses.

Questions:

- What are the weaknesses we have, individually and as a team?
- What our teammates should know about us?
- What are some obstacles we see ahead of us, that we are likely to face?

Examples:

- Team: Communication issues
- Easily Distracted
- Marie: creative, into visual arts but lacks organization and structure.

Step 8. Needs and Expectations

Make a list of the needs you have in order to be successful in this project. Think of this as a follow up to previous two sections where you have expressed your strengths and weaknesses as a team and as an individual. Now, you should be able to express the needs you have to improve the strengths you listed down.

Questions:

What does each member of the team need to be successful?
How the team could help each member with their needs?

Examples:

- Flexibility
- Status Updates
- Breaks
- Alone time

Step 9. Rules & Activities

Discuss with your team and agree on common rules and activities. Think of this as an outcome of the previous sections: a concrete set of rules and activities you as a team want to implement.

Questions:

What are the rules we want to introduce after doing this session?
How do we communicate and keep everyone up to date?
How do we make decisions?
How do we execute and evaluate what we do?

Examples:

- Weekly status updates
- Communication over Zoom
- Keeping meetings to 2 hours

Wrap Up

As you close this play, tell your team one single most important insight that you gained during this meeting.

Team Building in Action

Here is an example of how we filled in the Team Canvas Template in practice. You can use different Post-it colours for every person or use specific colour when its an input from the team as a whole or other colours when it is an individual input.

The Team Canvas

Most important things to talk about in the team to make sure your work as a group is productive, happy and stress-free

Team Name: CS2 Date: Jun 30 2021

v. 1.0 | English | theamcanvas.com

People & Roles

What are our names and the roles we have in the team?

- Mohammadreza - facilitator for co-creation process
- Wendy Ann - Designing the Playbook / Co-creation sessions
- Tavishi Guerita - CS2 Researcher (KWR)
- Joep - case study leader, facilitator of creative session with local stakeholders

Goals

What we want to achieve as a group? What are our key goals that are feasible, measurable and time-bounded?

- Get a first hand use of this session to adopt to the needs of the Case Study
- How to do the expectation session using Team Canvas

Values

What do we stand for? What are guiding principles? What are our common values that we want to be at the core of our work?

- Collaboration
- transparency
- Quality and Equality
- common understanding
- Play/ Creativity

Rules & Action Points

What are the rules we want to introduce after doing this session? How do we communicate and keep everyone up to date? How do we make decisions? How do we execute and evaluate what we do?

- Translation to Dutch
- Identifying the participants
- Best brainstorming medium for the stakeholders
- translate to NL and come up with examples pertinent to the case study/involved stakeholders
- To provide a playbook for this session the next two sessions

Personal Goals

What are our goals that we want to achieve as an individual?

- Understand team canvas and learn how to run/support a creative session
- learn how to run the creative session.
- Run a pilot
- learn what the outcomes of the creative session should be
- To deliver clear and useful co-creation tools

Needs & Expectations

What does each one of us need to be successful? What are our personal needs towards this session?

- Discuss conflicts openly
- Flexibility
- support with the process /tools such as this canvas
- time to digest
- Get feedback from the playbook users to improve it

Strengths & Assets

What are the skills we have in the team that we can leverage? What are our interpersonal/soft skills?

- Variety of stakeholders
- Easy to relate to the public
- strong knowledge position KWR
- Experience with design and co-creation process
- What are our strengths? Creativity / Arts / Design: Experience in Physical and Digital Art Installations
- facilitation
- interest/willingness from NGO - link to stakeholders and domain knowledge

Weaknesses & Development Areas

What are the weaknesses we have about us? What are some obstacles?

- stakeholders are not project partners - risk = commitment
- Get everyone on the same page
- KWR is - outsider in horticulture sector - not their own initiative
- availability of people
- Condense plays in a single session
- message different stakeholders want to communicate might conflict
- tendency not to be in the shoes of all the participants involved

miro

Team Canvas Template

PEOPLE & ROLES	COMMON GOALS
	PERSONAL GOALS
STRENGTH & ASSETS	

ADAPTED FROM: Team Canvas by Alex Ivanov and Mitya Voloshchuk. <http://theteamcanvas.com/>

Team Name

Date

VALUES

RULES & ACTIVITIES

PURPOSE

**EXPECTATIONS
& NEEDS**

WEAKNESSES & RISKS

Play 2:

Audience Empathy Map

Find out who the audiences are and what they say, do, feel, and think

Duration: 60 minutes

Participants: Team members, community

Location: Physical meeting room or online.

What is it?

Empathy Map is an essential tool in human-centred design used in capturing knowledge about a user's behaviors, attitudes and feelings. As co-creators, we need to know what our target audience would do or how they think. We can learn about them through research, observation, asking questions, and by stepping into their journeys. We can then synthesize all the extracted value to come up with real insights. Once we take the time to better understand the audience, we can empathise them more. When included in early project stages, this exercise helps teams enter the user's world and approach things from his or her perspective before ideating and developing solutions.

What needs to be done?

It is particularly useful to invite citizen participants in this play. Citizens can talk about the way they are affected by the issue and also the ways they can be part of the solution to the problem at hand.

The best empathy maps are drawn from real data. It is recommended that you observe people in the field prior to this session. Asking questions about their frustrations and aspirations can be a challenging task, but is worth your time and effort. The more you know about the subject, the more you need to look for patterns that will help you see your audience from a new point of view.

How are we doing it?

We will use Empathy Map as a tool that can help synthesize your team's collective knowledge and observation about your audience. In one visual map, it reveals deeper insights on the needs of the user. The benefits of this exercise include not only gaining knowledge about the audience but also creates a common understanding among your team.

We have provided a four quadrant map with questions as a template for you to print or guide you in freehand sketching your map. Each quadrant is labeled with a category that explores your audience's mindset and observable world: what they are doing, seeing, hearing, thinking, and feeling (including pains and gains). The team will work together to fill in the information with their own experience and knowledge of the audience.

Empathy Map can be used throughout the co-creation process and revisited as new data becomes available. A sparsely populated map that reveals more questions than answers indicates where more user research needs to be done.

Empathy mapping is only as reliable as the data you bring to the table, so make sure you brought data based on real observations.

Follow “**one persona per map**” rule. This means, if you have multiple personas, there should be an empathy map for each. Combining different personas in one map won't give you valuable insights.

Create context by first defining who will be the subject of the empathy map, and what they do and where they are located and other details; for example, “an activist living in cottage near the sea and protesting against water re-use”. Enriching the context allows you to empathise with the subject's current situation.

Instructions

Step 1. Set up the exercise.

On a whiteboard or a large flipchart, draw a 4-quadrant grid. Label the sections with “say,” “do,” “think,” and “feel,” respectively.

Sketch your user or stakeholder in the center. Give them a name and brief description of who they are and what they do.

Step 3. Find patterns and identify unknowns.

Within each quadrant, look for related items. If desired, move them closer together. As you do, imagine how these different aspects of your user’s life really affect how they feel - put yourself in their shoes.

Step 2: Write down your observations.

Populate the left-hand quadrants with Post-its that capture each of your individual observations— one Post-it per idea. Place observations of what people **do** in the lower-left quadrant, and place observations of what people **say** in the upper-left quadrant. Fill the right side with Post-its inferring what people **think** in the upper-right quadrant and what they **feel** in the lower-right quadrant.

Step 4. Step back and reflect.

Look at the map as a whole and draw conclusions or insights from what was written down and discuss about. What do you all agree on? What seems new or surprising? What’s missing? Are there contradictions or disconnects within or between quadrants? Any unexpected patterns? What, if any, latent human needs emerge?

Guide Questions

Here are some guide questions that can help you classify your observations about your audience.

Say

What are they saying about their environment? What are they saying about the local community? What do they see others saying and doing? What do they say about what they watch, hear and read? What do they say about what others are doing? What can we imagine them saying about the service?

Do

What behaviour can we observe them doing in public? What do they want to do? What do they need to do differently? What do they need to get done? What can we imagine them doing? What decisions do they need to make? How will we know they were successful?

Think

What do you think that your user might be thinking? What are their wants, their hopes, their needs, their desires or dreams? What does this tell you about his or her beliefs? What influences the way they think?

Feel

What situation is your user facing now? What emotions might your user be feeling? Take subtle cues like body language and their choice of words and tone of voice into account. What is his/her frustrations, fears and anxieties?

Empathy Map Template

Think

Feel

Play 3:

On-site Experience Safari and Shadowing

Immerse the team in the environment where the intervention will live

Duration: from 60 minutes to several days

Participants: Selected team members, public

Location: Field work

What is it?

The idea is to explore an imaginary intervention before we develop it or a similar, experience or service yourself. If it's an electrical bus ticket booking system, go ahead and buy a ticket and ride on the journey, or if it's a museum experience, then visit a science or space museum and try their exhibitions, hands-on activities and facilities on offer. Immersing ourselves in the service is key here as we aim to experience it from the user's perspective. This gives us a first hand understanding of what it feels like to be a user; what thoughts, frustrations and concerns your audience might be having at each stage, and discover potential opportunities for that experience or service, this process is called as **People Shadowing**. Using the same process, we can immerse ourselves totally in a particular environment so we can gain a first-hand perspective of the situation or context, this process on the other hand is called **Experience Safari**.

The fundamental aspect to this stage of the research is that it allows us to map out the various touchpoints and understand how everything fits together. We'll explore touchpoints, environments (e.g. kiosks, physical train station, museums, etc.), websites, apps and physical artefacts (e.g. a ticket, paperwork, etc). We'll also speak to customers, and employees, where possible, to get additional perspectives on the service.

How are we doing it?

We have provided a worksheet that shows some of the things you might want to record when doing an experience tour and shadowing. We recommend that you first explore the environment and observe. The idea is to reflect upon the experience and understand things and events surrounding the space. How did it made you feel, what happened, and what was going on around you. After reflecting on the tour, you can now look for a person to observe or follow.

You can complete one worksheet for every tour you make. On the same tour, fill out one worksheet for each person you actively got involved with, observed or followed. This is a structured way to compare your observations across the various persons that you shadowed and find connections or differences across various tours you made. The questions on the worksheet are examples, you can customise the worksheet to make it relevant to your project.

Experience Safari and Shadowing Worksheet

<p>Where</p> <p>.....</p> <p>DATE: TIME: FOCUS FOR THIS <u>EXPERIENCE TOUR</u>:</p> <p>DESCRIPTION OF THE SPACE / ENVIRONMENT:</p> <p>Other Observations:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>Practices observed</p> <p>People involved</p> <p>Products and objects they are using</p> <p>List or describe what works well in the space</p> <p>List or describe what doesn't work or needs improvement</p>
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<p>Who</p> <p>.....</p> <p>AGE GROUP: GENDER: REASON FOR <u>SHADOWING</u>:</p> <p>Key Findings:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>Personal Preference</p> <p>Concerns</p> <p>Existing Routines</p> <p>Activities</p> <p>Use of Objects</p> <p>Effect of Space</p>	<p>Who</p> <p>.....</p> <p>AGE GROUP: GENDER: REASON FOR <u>SHADOWING</u>:</p> <p>Key Findings:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>Personal Preference</p> <p>Concerns</p> <p>Existing Routines</p> <p>Activities</p> <p>Use of Objects</p> <p>Effect of Space</p>
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INSPIRED BY: Lovlie L.,Reason B.,Polaine A. (2013) Service Design: From Insight to Implementation. p54-p57. Rosenfeld Media

Harvesting data

Some of you will have a task of doing research work where you will map out various touchpoints in your experience tour and in the environment where the intervention will live. We'll use these findings to add a canvas to our strategy or framework until it reveals a reliable picture to us. We'll capture this information in our notes, or taken as photos. We might also collect artefacts such as tickets, brochures, maps, leaflets or any other material that we are faced with whilst experiencing a service.

To ideate a site specific artistic intervention, we would initially need to gather together the following data:

- The satellite view of the location of the intervention in Google maps.
- Architectural plan of the intervention site.
- Artefacts encountered whilst experiencing a tour to the intervention site.
- Cultural or historical aspect related to the location.
- Area statistics such as passersby, family, students, local amenities, crime rate, etc.
- Municipality regulations or rules such as noise control, social gatherings.
- Weather, temperature, season, etc.

Journey Map

While pretending to be a user, you can understand in detail all the aspects of the interaction with the service, observe how other people in the same space/environment behave, and eventually intercept the opinions and perceptions of other users. After having gone through the service, journey maps help generate a documentation of the experience that can be used for ideation purposes. The safari could be replicated going through other similar service as well.

Zane Gray

Fisherman

Scenario

Zane Gray is a Fisherman. He lives in Kalundborg near the coast. He visits the Kalundborg Havnepark to relax and enjoy the sun during summer. He joins the protest against raising demand of water from the industry.

Consider

He saw advertised on the street a new art intervention about water re-use and Technology happening at Kalundborg Havnepark and thought of taking a look.

To find details about the Art Intervention he checked their websites and Advertisements in the newspaper.

At the park

He saw that all the local amenities he was looking forward to use are still there.

He saw a new building in the place and entered looking for information. He was surprised on the modern style of the building.

He is also surprised to know that the building is using sustainable materials and is a place where the community can create campaigns for sustainability.

“ The Art Intervention shown in this website looks promising. I think i should go to the Park and have a look”

“ I wish to look for information about this building and what it stands for ”

Expectations

- A cozy place to relax and learn.
- Get favourable news from the government about their campaigns for conserving water at Kalundborg.
- Hesitant about water re-use and technology use.

Interacts

He entered the intervention space and out of curiosity and awe, Interacts with the art intervention and its surrounding.

He got immersed on those big and colorful graphic displays explaining Kalundborgs' plan towards water sustainability.

“ Now I understand more clearly what water re-use is all about and the future of Kalundborg will be like”

Signs Up

After completing his experience with the Art Intervention, he signs up to the active group promoting water re- use and regular activities.

“ It was such a nice experience, i wish to come back to this place again.”

Imagine

This is the third stage of the ULTIMATE Co-creation practice where we will imagine and create stories to develop visions of the future. We will ideate and create strategies to realise our objectives for this project.

Plays:

1

Problem-Solving Game

Through play we can learn to solve real-world challenges together.

2

Results Ideation

Ideate on how to make your intervention idea tangible.

3

Communication Scenario

Set the communication tone and voice of your intervention idea

Play 1:

Problem-Solving Game

Through play we can learn to solve real-world challenges together.

Duration: 60 minutes

Participants: Project team, community

Location: Preferrably in a physical meeting room

Aids with: Collaboration

What is it?

There are no winners or losers in a problem-solving games or activities. Sure, many games end up with a winner, but the true goal of these exercises is to break the ice, learn how to work as a team and to develop an open and agile mindset. The winning team of each game should share and reflect on team's strategies and thought process at the end of the exercise to help everyone learn and win.

How are we doing it?

We will use a paper pizza game concept to start with our work process because the challenges in the preparation of a pizza is something that most are familiar with and everyone can do. Its also a great way to stay away for a while from your current work environment.

Why do we have to collaborate?

In his book *The Fifth Discipline*, Peter Senge refers to “the staggering potential of collaborative learning – that collectively we can be more insightful, more intelligent than we can possibly be individually.” When individuals work together openly, processes and goals become more aligned, leading the group towards a higher success rate of achieving a common goal, thus better project results.

Paper Pizza Game

PREPARATIONS

Each team gets a printed template of various ingredient, paper of different colours, scissors and other materials. You will cut, shape and tape these together to form pizza slices according to the recipe of your choice. Form at least 3 to 4 persons per team. The game can be played with one team, but is more fun with more teams and a little healthy competition.

PIZZA RECIPE CONTENTS

- * Crust with outer edge folded upward
- * Tomato sauce/cheese. Don't skimp!
- * At least 3 slices of meat from pink stickies or from the template.
- * Some slices of pineapple/onion/sweet peppers cut from yellow or green stickies or from the template.
- * A spice or herb of your choice.

GAME FLOW

Step 1. Using paper pieces, build as many "quality" and aesthetically pleasing pizza slices as possible while trying to avoid paper waste.

Step 2. Give the Pizza a name.

Step 3. Design and cut a pizza plate

Step 4. When the time's up (about 15 minutes or so) clap your hands to inform the team to stop.

How about pizza quality?

Did the teams cut corners (perhaps literally)? Pizza bottoms should be the same size and well covered with tomato sauce, and the toppings should be nicely cut and distributed evenly.

In our ULTIMATE Lab, we have played this game ourselves and to determine the “Winner Pizza” we ask each team to bring forward their best pizza(s). Then ask the room to choose the most beautiful specimen. The “Winner Pizza” is placed in a prominent and visible place.

Play 2:

Results Ideation

Ideate on how to make your intervention idea tangible.

Duration: 120 - 150 minutes

Participants: Project team, community

Location: Preferably at a physical meeting room

Aids with: Collaboration, decision-making

What is it?

Begin with the results in mind. The Results Ideation provides a structured way to brainstorm as a team and project the effects of your intervention idea onto the future. This will help you reflect on what resources you may want to add, re-use, change, or retain.

What have you learned from the paper pizza game that you can relate in the real-world setting?

You can compare the process of cutting, shaping, and forming pieces of paper together to create recipes and crust of the pizza as an ideation process. A challenge was given during the activity to create a quality and aesthetically pleasing pizza and your next step as a team is to think of creating something based on the materials provided to you. Generating a solution to come up with an intervention idea is a similar process. You first have to identify and describe the challenge you have in your project then find potential intervention solution based on the resources you have at hand.

Challenge

1. Describe the challenge your project is facing.

This is comparable to the challenges in making your pizza, think of the needs of the people eating the pizza, are there reported allergies to some food? Are they vegan? Do you need to use a gluten-free bread?

Intervention App

2. Describe your chosen immersive app, intervention, or action

Value

3. What needs, enhancements the intervention app will cater to. How might we enhance our value proposition by designing for sustainability and continuous evolution and adaptation?

Think of the ingredients that adds value to the taste of your pizza. Perhaps think of adding spices?

Re-Use

5. Can the intervention app be re-used by the community? How? How resources can be reduced or not used at all?

Think of preparing a holistic pizza. Some like it with tomato, some with cheese only. Some prefer spicy, some prefer it sweet. How will you cater to these preferences without preparing different pizzas.

For instance, an interactive webpage campaign can be re-used not just to convey plan of action but can also serve as a platform for inviting the community to take part in organized activities.

Visualise

6. After thinking of a more sustainable and community-driven options in Steps 5 and 6, draw how the intervention app would look like in the actual environment.

Resources

4. What are the resources your intervention will use and what is available within your reach?

Think what is it built upon? How do you want it to be shown, in a mobile phone, an immersive screen, on the Internet or public space like a park. How will you maintain the intervention app? How might we provide a circular afterlife?

Replace

6. Can the needs be satisfied differently? How?
For instance, how will you make it more inclusive, sustainable, and re-usable in another way?

Think of the final product of your pizza game. What makes the “winning pizza” stand out.

We have provided a filled template for you to think together as a team on what needs of your case study does your intervention idea might fulfill. The goal of explaining them as if they are a pizza game is unblock people from shying away from digital solutions and generate collective motivation to creatively tackle and contribute to the challenge.

Hand the water...
 INLINE...
 DEMAND...
 For water...
 For 8th...
 WINTER PARK...
 GYM...
 SWIMMING POOL...
 CEILING...
 WATER...
VIRTUAL ICE

CHEAP SODA

The idea is to build the machine which is a process

1. An automated machine...
2. An idea to build with...
3. An idea to build...

to drinking water

- ...
- ...
- ...

AR APP
 USER PLAY BUTTON
 SELFIE
 LIVE TWEET
 COLOR FILTER

YOUTH
 YOUTH
 MAKE TAKE
 ONT REACH

Results Ideation Template

Team Name

Date

Vizualize

Instructions

1. On the template provided, write together the challenges your project is facing.
2. Choose a service intervention idea / digital app that everyone has some form of familiarity with. For instance, an interactive campaign story web app, and place it in a circle.
3. What needs of the case study does this chosen intervention app fulfill?
4. What resources does the intervention app use?
5. Can the intervention app and its resources be re-used by the community?
6. Ideate on how the needs can be met differently, more inclusive and sustainable in another way. For instance, the intervention app can provide more sustainable alternatives to present a service
7. In the end, taking into account your ideas for fulfilling needs differently and resource use, draw how your intervention app could solve your challenges.

If you have more than one idea of an intervention app that can solve your challenge, brainstorm on a separate template.

Play 3:

Communication Scenarios

Ideate on how to make your intervention idea tangible.

Duration: 120 minutes

Participants: Project team, community

Location: Preferably in a physical meeting room

Aids with: Collaboration, decision-making

What is it?

It is important to reflect on your message and its possible interpretation with your target audience using the intervention app that you co-designed in our previous play. We can do that by imagining possible communication scenarios. This play is designed to find the answer to the question.

How might we bring our message to our audience in a playful and creative way?

Instructions

1. Tell the story of the scenario you desire to communicate.
2. Write the message that reflects the communication scenario that you described. Reflect on how your intervention idea will convey the message.
3. Write the tone that you want to use to tell your message. Tone of voice is the brand personality of your intervention idea. The tone is simply the way you speak the message to help your audience better receive them.

Here is how you can tell the story of your communication scenario:

1. Our industry is looking forward to be more responsible in our community. We can work together to solve our use of water challenges. Together we will build a more sustainable water and greener environment.

How does this voice sound like to you?

Tone: Friendly, Optimistic, Formal.

2. We are initiating a green energy campaign. We are asking all to upgrade on time. Don't waste our time if you're not willing to cooperate, we will take action on vehicles that won't comply.

Tone: Informative, Angry, Accusatory.

4. Reflect what might be the perception of your target audience. You can imagine to yourself how you'd view or hear these messages if you received them.
5. Reflect on the side effects or adverse risks of the message. If needed, adjust your message to reverse the identified risks.

Communication Scenario

Tell the story of the scenario you desire to implement.

What is the message you wish to communicate? Reflect how it goes well with your intervention app idea.

Message

Tone

What sort of tone do you want to use to communicate your message? Why?

Team Name

Date

What might be the perception of the target audience?
How will the message influence their behaviour?

Perception

Risks

Reflect on the potential risks or effects of the message such as creating confusion, disrupting the social environment. How will you handle that?

Reflect

Participants reflect on the process of the co-creation, and consider what worked well and what could be improved. This can include testing their prototype and going out in the field to assess potential failures and successes. This might require the participants to repeat stages, or return to previous phases such as "Build" to revise or learn from their previous approach.

Plays:

1

Reflection

Reflect on the process of co-creation to learn from what went well and what can be improved.

2

Prototype Appraisal

Get feedback in the field to assess potential failures and successes of the project.

Play 1:

Reflection

Reflect on the process of co-creation to learn from what went well and what did not so far.

Duration: 30 - 45 minutes

Participants: All involved in the project

Location: Physical meeting room or online

What is it?

It is important to go through a period of reflection to identify what worked well, and what could be improved. In this way, we can look back on the process and discuss together. You might consider how you would use the methods and protocols differently, or how you might approach your challenges in another way.

What needs to be done?

Citizen participants and the coordinating organization should take time to sit together and think back on the whole process to date. We recommend that you allocate some time to reflect at the end of a each meeting to keep everyone on the same page. It is also good to know if the expectations of each participants in this co-creation practice have changed over the course of time. We can also reflect on how we can build on the lessons we have learned so far.

How are we doing it?

We will be asking our team simple questions before we start co-creating together and after each plays. This will help us gauge the strengths and weaknesses of the project. This is will enable us to know if the activities brought forth any meaningful impact to each and everyone involved.

Instructions

Step 1.

At the start of your meeting, ask each participants about their hopes and expectations in relation to the project. What do they hope to learn? Why are they taking part in this co-creation? At the end of your meetings, look back to see if their expectations were met.

Step 2.

As the co-creation activities unfold. Follow up your reflection questions on what they hope to achieve at the current moment. Are they satisfied or feeling worried in relation to the solutions to the issues they identified and in the way and the project has unfolded.

Step 3.

Coordinators or activity leader can reflect on the suitability of the venues, meeting schedule with reference to your project milestones.

Step 4.

Consider your future steps, what the participants learned, the skills they acquired, and how might your experiences might be improved. Reflecting on what worked well and what not in the current co-creation practice, we can consider how we would use the methods and tools differently in the the next stages.

Before

1. What do you expect to learn out of this project?
2. What do you expect to get out of the current exercise?

After

1. What did you learn from this meeting?
2. What did you wish you have learned?
3. What do you think went well?
4. What areas do you think we can improve more?

Play 2:

Prototype Appraisal

Get feedback in the field to access potential failures and successes of the project.

Duration: 30 - 45 minutes

Participants: Project team, community, and experts

Location: Fieldwork, physical meeting room

What is it?

By evaluating the prototype that we have created together and asking users about their experience, will help us further measure the strengths and weaknesses of the project.

What needs to be done?

This can include testing your prototype and going out in the field as a team to access potential failures and successes. This might require you to repeat stages, or return to previous phases such as "Build" to revise your previous approach.

How are we doing it?

Set up a safe environment for the team to talk about positive experiences and frustrations with the prototype. Record everything.

Instructions

Step 1.

Go out of the field, show, and ask users about their experience of the prototype you made. Ask them, what will make you, as a user, adapt or gain motivation to use our project? What went well and what did not?

Step 2.

As a team, set a discussion table. Set up a safe environment where everyone can openly talk about both the pain and gain points of the prototype: the positive and negative experiences of the users with the prototype; both observed and recorded.

Step 3.

Using stickies, write down short description of the stages of the user experience while interacting or using your prototype. Remind yourself of the user-journey play that you co-created together during the Understand Module.

Step 4.

Consider your future step, what have you learned, the skills you acquired, how might we improve your experience? Reflecting on what worked well and what not in the current co-creation practice, we can consider how we would use the methods and tools differently in the the next stages.

Step 5.

Assign one colour of sticky notes for positive and enjoyable experiences and another colour for frustrating ones. Discuss amongst each other how you can use what you have learned to improve the prototype.

TEST AND GET FEEDBACK

Showing your prototype into the hands of the real audience and getting feedback is the first step toward improving the solution to your challenge.

Feedback will equip you to understand what's working, and gain inspiration on how to make your idea work better.

REFLECT AND CO-CREATE

Reflect with your team and re-focus based on your findings. Next, bring the very people you're co-designing for into the re-designing process and get them to make things right alongside your new findings.

INTEGRATE FEEDBACK AND ITERATE ON THE FLY

Synthesize what you've learned during the testing to see what changes to prioritise and implement into the next version.

Iterate on this cycle of testing, learning, and evolving to refine your idea and solution.

Before

1. What do you expect to get out of the current task?

After

1. What did you learn from this task?
2. What do you think went well in your prototype?
3. What do you think can be improved?
4. What do you think are the strengths and weaknesses of the project?

Build

In this stage, participants work together to propose courses of action and solutions. It is important that an expert in immersive narrative intervention is involved here to guide the participants on prototyping design concepts. A prototype is a draft version of a service, product or intervention that allows participants to explore the ideas they work on together and be able to demonstrate a proof of concept before investing time and money into development.

Play 1:

Prototype

Sketch and demonstrate actions that can lead to change.

Duration: 120 minutes

Participants: Project team, community, and experts

Location: Physical meeting room

What is it?

Once you have identified your problem, understand your target audience and have gathered data about the environment, and have identified where action is needed or where you think you can effect change, we now create initial demonstrations of these actions that can lead to change. These can take many forms, including campaigns, artistic interventions, public forums and presentations.

At this stage, your plan of actions should involve the community, and are most effective when carried out in your local community.

How are we doing it?

Depending on the result in the Imagine module, we will provide participants selected demonstrations and Immersive narrative digital tools to bring their ideas to life. This will allow them to both physically sketch out their concept and digitally prototype their own design concepts based on the scenarios they laid out during the Imagine phase. The aim of this stage is to create a prototype of an immersive narrative solution in order to test ideas and show its impact to the target audiences.

Storyboard

Quick Design

INSPIRATIONAL IMMERSIVE NARRATIVE DEMOS

Relate a Story

Once you have identified where action is needed or where you think you can effect change in the previous stages, discuss amongst each other a related story or an instance when you felt the importance of supporting such action.

Show

Show amongst your team something that can make you feel engaged or otherwise disinterested in an action, campaign, art intervention or an initiative with societal or environmental cause? What can you do to reverse that?

Get Feedback

Integrate Feedback and Iterate

You can combine the previous immersive demos that we presented and your own research to inspire you to build your prototype.

Sketch

Draw a picture of what will make you interested, connected or engaged in an immersive intervention idea on the top part of a paper, and draw what makes you disconnected or disengaged on the bottom part of it. Discuss what you drew as a team.

Build

We will use our cardboard, post-its, coloured pens, your story, your sketches and creativity to build your first prototype.

We don't need to go deeper about technical details now but a knowledge will be a useful input in building stories and scenarios. You can extend or build upon the inspiration physical concepts we have shown.

Analyse

Using all the data gathered during Understand and Imagine phase, information is analysed and discussed amongst the experts in the team and the Case Study. Bringing this information together is important for identifying areas for action and change. The aim is to build a collective understanding of the data.

Play:

1

Innovation Playground Strategy

Synthesize all inputs and data together to determine the final design of your intervention or action.

Play 1:

Innovation Playground Strategy

Synthesize all inputs and data together to determine the final design of your intervention or action.

Duration: 120 minutes

Participants: Project team

Location: Preferrably in a physical meeting room

Aids with: Decision-making

What is it?

By evaluating the prototype that we have created together and asking users about their experience, will help us further measure the strengths and weaknesses of the project.

What needs to be done?

Once you have identified where action is needed or where you think you can effect change, it is important to synthesize all inputs and data together to find patterns and help your team in decision-making. It will also aid the team to identify what sort of action is needed and where it should take place. An action can take various forms such as a campaign, an artistic intervention, or a public presentation, it is important to decide which one best solves your issue.

The team should decide what the next steps should be based on insights they have gleaned from synthesizing all inputs and data.

Instructions

In this play, we will analyse the data in a collage. A collage is an assembly of different forms, materials and sources creating a new whole. So, bring out all the output data that you have collected from the Understand module especially from the On-site Safari and Shadowing play. Keep other outputs from previous modules as a reference when needed.

1. What is our purpose?

Innovation begins with defining goals and objectives. It's best to start at the end. Decide where we want to get to, ask everyone what our success would look like, and then work towards the present, one step at a time, to figure out the barriers and challenges that need to be addressed to achieve our goal.

2. Where is the right playground?

Identifying the place our intervention or play will live and the demographics we are targeting to create the right playground for citizens' participation in a neighbourhood community is of crucial importance for cities to effectively deal with future transformations. One condition to meet this is to have access to the communication channels present. Another is to understand the local context of the place, the audience, and neighbourhood networks; which an approach we call "Place by Design".

3. How are we going to win and create value by playing?

We create value by bringing together play, participation, creativity and the community. Consider the name "creative placemaking", an approach which brings sense of community, participation, identity and culture together. This involves considering the public space and the neighbourhood community as an inseparable ingredient for a successful place.

4. What resources can be re-used, enhanced or replaced to win?

We use the flexible and user-driven orientation towards space using the “Multi-use Playspace” model to accelerate learning and new ways of doing things by providing resources, facilities, infrastructures or loose parts that players could readily use, re-use, move around, and manipulate. Allowing the community to create their own makeshift interventions, activities or events.

5. What structures, bridges, and measures can support choices?

We identify needed support, management systems, find common grounds, and knowledge creation to bridge the gaps that exist between play, participation and innovation; the “Bridge the Play Gap” approach. This is to ensure that everyone is working towards the same goal and aspirations throughout our co-creation process.

When working with a large team, it is important that process is facilitated in a way that allows everyone to be on the same page. Just take turns in adding information or evidences on the wall. A leader can put similar things together if necessary. The output of this play, which is a collage wall plays a role in guiding the players to the identification of patterns and findings, and then later will serve as a knowledge that can be shared to others as insights and ideas develop.

Innovation Playground Strategy

Innovation strategy to create engaged communities and urban playgrounds for citizens to meet, interact, and collaborate.

INSPIRED BY: Lafley & Martin (2013). Playing to Win: How Strategy Really Works. Brilliance Corporation.

Synthesis Wall in Action

Innovation Playground Strategy (Adopted from +CityxChange EU Project). This framework can be seen as an innovation strategy to create engaged communities and urban playgrounds for citizens to meet, interact and collaborate. The framework helps to picture what capabilities and resources needed to successfully develop a playable city leading to an immersive narrative intervention. In this play, we will create a collage wall or cluster of important insights about users, artifacts, places, and connections to inform and inspire the design process.

Don't forget to define a structure to place the notes on the wall before starting the analysis. We used the 5-point questions on the Innovation Playground Strategy to cluster and structure information.

We wrote down on post-it notes all relevant information from the research data and input gathered from the previous stages and organized them on the wall in order to begin identifying important insights and relevant themes.

Legacy

This stage or module is all about envisioning the future of the project and making a plan for lasting impact. Plans for sharing information should be included to ensure that the project is sustainable. Experiences, lessons learned, tools and methodologies of the project are disseminated.

Champion`s Recognition

Community Champions lead and inspire others to engage—and make a difference by demonstrating how to make a positive change in the community. Building lasting relationships and teams that cultivate connection, creating impact and strengthening their neighborhoods and business at the same time.

Nurture your Community Champions by celebrating their achievements of being a great contributor to this co-creation practice.

YOUR NAME HERE

This legacy recognizes citizens who have gone above and beyond their local communities. Thank you for your inspiring engagement and for championing a co-creation practice to strengthen your neighbourhood.

You become our dedicated Community Champion who is actively contributing to the improvement of your community. Through your contributions in a co-creation leading to an immersive narrative intervention, you become a solution in bringing forth positive social change to a wider audience.

The ULTIMATE Team looks forward to a collaborate with you again in the future.

ULTIMATE

WATER SMART INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

TEAM COORDINATOR

Ice Breaker

We include social plays in this playbook that you can use to have people meet each other and get to know some of the larger group. Build a sense of community and accountability towards each other and the project. These plays illustrate how working together can bring about out of the box innovations.

Play 1

Remote Check-In

What is it?

Invites each member in a group to be present, seen, and heard in a remote environment. Checking-in increases presence and engagement.

How?

Step 1: Craft the check-in question or choose from the options provided in the Simplified Playbook Deck section.

Think of a question that will connect and support the team to feel seen or heard. Think of what kind of tone do you want to create. Is it playful, serious, or connecting? Do you want to learn something new about each other?

You can also think of how the check-in question that connects and supports the rest of the agenda and the overall purpose of the meeting.

Step 2: As a Facilitator, start the session by asking the theme question.

My heart as red as an apple!

My head is somewhere between yellow and mellow

Step 3 :

Be Organic.
Welcome participants to take their turn whenever they are ready.

Play 2

Campfire

What is it?

New collaborations are spent in meeting sessions, reading guides, and playing online games to learn the know-how for their new challenges. But the reality is that the bulk of collaborative work knowledge is gained through social experience.

It's a great way to get to know each other through storytelling, brainstorming, and working on the fly. In the corporate real world we also face challenges and limitations and make the use of the whatever resources available when under deadline or pressure.

How?

Step 1. Warm up the participants by introducing the campfire activity.

Step 2. “Gather the fire woods” session. After making an introduction of this activity, take 16–20 words or phrases you can use as trigger words to start the storytelling session. Make your own “wall of words” or continue on the “wall of words” example that we have provided here.

WALL OF WORDS

This is a “campfire” and you are invited to share and associate stories back and forth.

You can suggest familiar themes for instance a social trip at the woods, first collaborative meeting, a company visit. Prepare some words (nouns and adjectives) and involve the group to add more. Update the wall.

Step 3. Reflect on the “wall of words”. Take a few minutes to think of a story associated with one or few of them.

Step 4. Set the “Camp on fire”. Start the storytelling session yourself by taking one of the words on the “wall of words” and presenting it.

Now, look at the “wall of words” and imagine a story ...

The story is our first field visit to a use-case site where nearby River turned cloudy white triggering anger in the community.

STORY THREAD

Step 5. Ask others to continue what you started by taking another word from the “Wall of Words” and posting it to the “Story Thread” template.

WALL OF WORDS

Who will volunteer next?

I can take the turn!

This is fun, I want to participate more...

Step 6. Before the first player begins his / her story, give instructions to everyone on how they should navigate in this session, as in the dialogue:

That word from his story reminds me of something, let me write and

Jot down a word or a phrase on a sticky note that can remind them of another related story. You can use this word to continue the story or pull a sticky note from the “wall of words”

Before you begin your story, please read aloud the word you choose. Other players, please listen carefully to the story.

Step 7. Document everything and show it on your wall. Repeat this process until the players have created a snake-like “story thread” which acts as an archive of the campfire conversation.

 You can use the “story thread” to share the resulting story of your group in the next 10 minute discussion / reporting back session. Use your best judgment to determine when to end this storytelling session.

Step 8: Prepare to “put out the fire” (end the session) by “checking-out” with your group.

Before we “put out” the fire, please let me know if there are any insights, learnings, or final thoughts you want to share.

Play Guidelines

Part 1: Introduction and Check - In (10 mins)

1. Facilitator introduces themselves and describes the “check-In” question, and invites everyone to introduce themselves and respond to the “check-in” question – ask people to turn on their cameras and unmute when it is their turn to speak.

After introducing the names of the participants, location and job title, you can start to “check-In” and ask the participants to answer the question.

Option 1. Ask the participants to share where their head and heart is today?

Option 2. What colour mood is in your head and heart today?

Option 3. How have they been doing with the pandemic and working from home?

2. For any of these questions options you choose, remind your participants to give a very short answer or description of how they feel. (1 minute each).

For Example:

“Hi my name is Lisa, I live in The Hague, and I currently work at KWR.
Today, my head is focused and my heart feels full.”

3. Please feel free to use our check-In question template and show it to your participants.

Check - In Question

What colour
mood is in
your head and
heart today?

Part 2: CampFire (40 mins)

1. Present the activity.

For Example:

“Campfire is a fun way to get to know each other and to create a story together, we will think of words, then use these words to craft our story together, each person taking a turn to add to the story.”

2. Ask the participants to think of a word or a phrase and write them in the “wall of words”.
3. Reflect on the “wall of words”. Ask participants to spend approx. 1-3 minutes to pick one word in the “wall of words” and reflect on what kind of story they would tell with those words – individual reflection.
4. Facilitator picks 1-2 words to start with the story (modify the option’s storyline as you want).

Options:

1. **Woods:** Ultimate Search: A group’s social trip in the woods and have forgotten to bring a compass; no Internet, no GPS;
2. **River:** Ultimate Adventure: Ultimate’s visit to a use-case partner where nearby river turns cloudy white and residents are not happy;
3. **Computer:** Goodbye Computer: It’s Ultimate project’s deadline, all computer documents are inaccessible and everyone has to rely on 3 means - human memory, pen and paper.
4. **Water:** Create your own version of Godard’s “Story of Water”: A story of a character attempting to make her way from her home country to the City, amid a massive flood. She travelled by foot, by boat then met a person with a car.

If one of your team is more comfortable in another language than English, ask them to share a word in their own language, and this could be a learning opportunity for others and to add it to the story.

6. Add the picked words to the “Story Thread” template as an archive of the story.

6. Keep going around until all the words are used up (or use your judgement) and can flow organically from there.

7. End the story before leaving the break-out rooms and check-out with the members on the story and how they felt.

Story Thread

Wall of Words

Lighthouse

water

murky

stone

trees

cat

fun

cloudy

overflowing

dense woods

animal sound

boat

Insights

Sustainable Co-creation. It is important to bring the community on board or to validate every key decisions before taking the next steps. Whenever you need to initiate a new process or something needs to be tested or changed, keep the community informed and heard. It may not always sound easy and there may be differences on views every now and then. Everyone in a co-creating team need to work hard to find a compromise. Effective team strives consensus, and strong management skills can be useful asset in a team to support the co-existence of different views. Despite these challenges, collaboration is the best method to halt the tradition where people at the top decides independently for a project while alienating community members.

Case Studies

We will add the results of the Case Study co-creation practice in this section in the next version of this playbook.

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